

Enhancing Science Journals Availability and Use in Federal University Libraries

Mohammed Suleiman NUHU (CLN)

Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute, Abuja
nuhusuleiman@nbrri.gov.ng

Hadiza Anave ABDULAZIZ

Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute, Abuja
haa4sure@yahoo.com

Abstract

The study investigated the availability and use of science journals at Federal University Otuoke Library, Bayelsa State. Five research questions guided the study, and the data collection instrument used was a structured questionnaire; the study adopted a survey research method. The study's findings show that most respondents use science journals twice monthly and monthly and purposely use them for self-examination, learning more about a subject, assignments, and coursework. The study also shows that science journals are readily available and accessible to the respondents. However, most respondents indicated that science journals help direct and guide them on how to carry out research and do quality research. The study revealed that the majority of the respondent encountered challenges with the changes in journal frequency, numbering, titles and format and lack of science journals in their course of discipline. Therefore, the study recommends that university libraries should endeavour to maintain continuous subscriptions to science journals and make them available in all fields of knowledge to encourage students' effective use.

Keywords: Availability, Use, Science journals, University Libraries, Nigeria

Introduction

One of the objectives of setting up a university is to encourage and promote scholarship and conduct research in all fields of learning and human endeavour. In every university setting, the three major components that drive its day-to-day activities are teachers/classrooms, laboratories and libraries (Bibrowek, 2014). Among these three components, the library is uniquely positioned as a potential educational force. For this role, library holdings are organized for maximum exploitation by users. The effectiveness of a library as an instrument of education is determined by the success with which it can provide the user with the information he/she seeks. The library can fulfil this function best by pursuing a policy of constant self-evaluation to be alert to the changing needs of its users. It is, perhaps, in consideration of the role of the libraries, that universities pay special attention to building and equipping them.

University libraries invest vast amounts of money yearly in purchasing, processing and storing information resources to serve their users while adapting to their changing information-seeking behaviour (Irenoa & Sawyerr-George, 2022). Singh and Kaur (2009) stressed that preservation and access to knowledge and information are the primary mandates of university libraries, alongside supporting the mission of their parent institutions, which is teaching and research. Scholars such as Adeleke (2015) and Apotiade (2002) have emphasized the crucial role of university libraries in research and scholarship in institutions of higher learning. Many times,

university libraries have been referred to as the heart or nerve centres of institutions of higher learning where all academic activities revolve. The mission and vision of university libraries in the university setting

The availability of science journals in academic libraries is essential to students' research development in academic institutions; it is tantamount to their academic growth and success. It is an effective and efficient primary source for good research. However, a well-stocked and developed serial section of the library is a source of pride for any academic institution that will help support and strengthen teaching, learning, and research. Therefore, maintaining constant and continuous journal subscriptions in university libraries poses a serious challenge to library management. Edelson (1998) asserts that the world of science journals - made up of authors, readers, librarians, and publishers headed for seismic upheavals that must result in significant alterations in the landscape. Librarians, hit with declining budgets and escalating journal prices, cancel subscriptions. Publishers, facing declining subscription levels, raise rates to compensate, and then some. The increase in the output of research papers balloons the size and cost of journals. The subscription backlog of science journals in most university libraries is still a perturbing issue in serial building in academic libraries in developing countries.

University libraries should endeavour to provide and make available current and relevant science journal titles in all the courses offered by the parent institution. They should also create awareness of their availability in the library to increase their effective use. This study investigates the availability and utilization of science journals at Federal University Otuoke Library, Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

University libraries invest huge amounts of money every year to purchase, process and store information resources to serve their users (Akporhonor, 2015). Singh and Kaur (2009) stressed that preservation and access to knowledge and information are the central mandates of university libraries, alongside supporting the mission of their parent institutions, teaching and research. Scholars such as Adeleke (2015) and Apotiade (2002) have emphasized the crucial role of university libraries in research and scholarship in institutions of higher learning. Many times, university libraries have been referred to as the heart or nerve centres of institutions of higher learning where all academic activities revolve. The mission and vision of university libraries in the university setting

However, the decline in library material and service usage at the university level suggests that library users are looking elsewhere for information resources. The libraries are losing clientele; the researcher observed that library users in the study area seemed to prefer going elsewhere for their information needs due to the explosion of information and Internet use.

Science journals are the most crucial serial publications that have highly projected research publications to academic institutions. However, their limited availability in university libraries and use by students form the basis for this study. Therefore, the study investigated users' availability and use of science journals at Federal University Otuoke Library, Bayelsa State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the availability and utilization of science journals in the Federal University Otuoke Library in Bayelsa State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the frequency of use of science journal

2. ascertain the purpose of use of science journals
3. find out the availability of science journals in the university library
4. ascertain the accessibility of science journals in the university library
5. determine the importance of science journals to users

Literature Review

Modern science communication relies heavily on books, monographs, and conference proceedings, but most commonly on academic journals (Oluronsola, 2001). The journal is fundamental to science communication. The status conferred by publication in highly-rated journals is essential to the career of academics (Mohammed, 2008). A science journal is a periodical that disseminates current findings originating from intellectual and creative work of research of a discipline, sub-discipline, interdisciplinary and multidiscipline, usually published yearly, quarterly, bimonthly, or monthly issues sold by subscription. Also, Milne (1999) defined science communication as "the social phenomenon whereby intellectual and creative activity is passed from one scholar to another." According to Reitz (2004), a journal is a periodical devoted to disseminating original research and commentary on current developments within a specific discipline, sub-discipline or field of study (for example, *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*), usually published quarterly, bimonthly, or monthly issues sold by subscription. Yahaya (1993) refers journals to those periodicals created by any of the following:

- A constituted body: an educational institution, ministry, board, bureau, council, commission, library, centre, academy, division, or department.
- A specialized group: scientists, historians, educators, economists, archaeologists, linguists, folklorists, medical doctors
- An interest group: student associations, religious groups, trade unions.

The main purpose of a science journal is to publish recent original research findings to the academic communities. Experts in the field usually write journal articles. They are current and usually narrowly focused; references are included to show the sources of information consulted and also the use of the vocabulary of the discipline, assuming some background on the part of the read is highly regarded. Submitted articles are often "peer-reviewed" by the editorial body, which agrees that the article represents properly conducted original research or writing before it is accepted for publication by the university presses or professional organizations. Science journals are also academic, professional, peer-reviewed, or refereed. Thus, science journal articles should possess the following elements to have full academic recognition:

- a) Abstract
- b) Introduction
- c) Literature review
- d) Research Methodology
- e) Analysis of findings includes tables, graphs, and charts, but few glossy pages or exciting pictures.
- f) Conclusion and Recommendations
- g) References.

Therefore, university libraries should provide students with the latest journal titles in all the subjects/courses covered by its parent institution, and staff and students are expected to make good use of the library to get current information in their chosen field of study. In the words of Olanlokun and Salisu (1988), journals are accorded prominence in the library because they provide the latest information in a discipline and if people want to be current in their field, they have to read relevant journals.

The availability of science journals refers to journal publications in the library. Aguolu and Aguolu (2002) assert that resources may be available in the library and even identified bibliographically as relevant to one's interest. However, the user may not be able to lay hands on them. One may identify citations in indexes but may not have access to the sources containing the relevant article. They further maintain that the availability of an information source does not necessarily imply its accessibility because the source may be available, but access to it is prevented for one reason or another. However, since the university library is the repository base of information resources of its parent institution, it is saddled with the responsibility to provide and make adequate information resources available.

Science journals are arranged alphabetically or in subject order on the shelf in proper journal management and organisation. Also, university libraries usually bind all the issues for a given publication year in one or more volumes to preserve and create adequate access for users interested in using a particular journal title. It is improbable that the science journal will retain its current format as the world evolves from print to digital electronic form. As libraries transition, academic journals will be swept along with the process. Science journals have reasons of their own to make the conversion (Seiler, 1990). Therein, science journals are presently available in digital format in full-text bibliographic databases, usually by licensing agreement.

Information and communication technology (ICT) is gaining momentum in university libraries, especially now that most universities in Nigeria are adopting ICT in developing and improving their services (Oriogu, Ogbuiyi & Ogbuiyi, 2014). The advent of ICT has revolutionized the mode of collection building in academic libraries in that the emergence of the Internet has greatly improved the means of science access, use and availability in university libraries. This paradigm shift has greatly affected users' information-seeking behaviour. Therein, the rapid post-World War II expansion of STM research was characterized by the ensuing commercialization of science publishing and an increase in subscription fees, far exceeding library acquisition budgets. This has resulted in a funding crisis that has strained the symbiotic relationship among publishers, academic libraries and scholars. In this environment of rising tensions, with the evolution of digital networks in 1993, it became technically feasible to move from a paper to a digital distribution system for science journals (Solomon, 2013). However, licensing of electronic resources has been very common, but presently, the trend has loosened to open access mode. There are two main forms of open access: Open access publishing, in which the journals are freely available from the Internet, and self-archiving, where the author makes copies of their work freely available on the web. Despite the promising potential for open access to improve science communication, this mode of publishing is not yet widespread in developing countries when compared to developed countries (Moller, 2006; Wang & Su, 2006; Directory of Open Access Repositories (DOAR), 2010). Subscription to paper and online science journals by university libraries remains paramount for providing adequate access to available science research works to students in academic communities.

Methodology

A survey research method was adopted for the study, and structured questionnaires were used to collect data. A total of 290 science students constituted the population of the study. A purposive sampling technique was used to sample one hundred and fifty (150) science students of Federal University Otuoke Library, Bayelsa State; frequency counts, simple percentages,

mean, and standard deviation were used to answer the study's objectives. The study covers the frequency of use of science journals, the purpose of use of science journals, and the availability of science journals in the university library. It also covers the accessibility of science journals in the university library, the importance of science journals to users, and the challenges of using them.

Analysis of Findings

The results of the data collected and analysed are presented. The results are presented according to the research questions formulated for the study. The Summary of the findings of the study is also presented.

Return Rate

The return rate of this study showed that out of the 150 questionnaires administered to science students, 149 copies were filled and returned. This represents a return rate of 99%. This was considered appropriate for analysis because the non-returned rate was too meagre to affect the study's outcome. Table 1 explains the distribution of the questionnaires by level

Table 1: Return Rate by Level

Statements	Frequency	Percentage
100level	6	4.3
200level	5	3.5
300level	84	58.7
400level	48	33.5
Total	143	100.0

Table 1 shows that 6(4.3%) are in 100 Level, 5(3.5%) are in 200 Level, 84(58.7%) are in 300 Level, 48(33.5%) are in 400 Level.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the frequency of use of science journals?

Table 2: Frequency of use of science journals

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	22	15.4
Weekly	22	15.4
Monthly	43	30.1
Twice monthly	41	28.7
Never	15	10.4
Total	143	100.0

Table 2 shows the items' ratings on the frequency of use of science journals: daily 22 (15.4), Weekly 22 (15.4), Monthly 43 (30.1), twice monthly 41 (28.7), and never 15(10.4).

Research Question 2: What is the purpose of using science journals?

Table 3: Purpose of use of science journals

Items	Yes	Somewhat	Never	Mean	Std. D.
For examination	56 (37.6%)	69 (46.3%)	24 (16.1%)	1.79	703

For self-development	70 (47.0%)	66 (44.3%)	13 (8.7%)	1.62	643
Learning more about a subject	93 (62.4%)	43 (28.9%)	13 (8.7%)	1.45	620
For assignment/coursework	92 (61.7%)	47 (31.5%)	10 (6.7%)	2.20	930
For pleasure and relaxation	32 (21.5%)	45 (30.2%)	72 (48.3%)	1.40	743

Table 3 shows the rating of the items on the purpose of using science journals as follows: For assignment /coursework (Mean =2.20) was ranked highest in the mean score rating and was followed by for examination (Mean =1.79), For self-development (Mean =1.62), Learning more about a subject (Mean =1.45), and lastly, For pleasure and relaxation (Mean =2.09).

Research Question 3: To what extent are science journals available?

Table 4: Availability of Science Journals

S/N	Items	Available	Not Available	Mean	Std. D.
1	Biology journals	132 (88.6%)	17 (11.4%)	.97	.357
2	Microbiology journals.	142 (95.3%)	7 (4.7%)	1.07	.361
3	Chemistry Journals	134 (89.9%)	15 (10.1%)	.97	.441
4	Biochemistry Journals	137 (91.9%)	12 (8.1%)	1.02	.500
5	Mathematics/Statistics Journals	129 (86.6%)	20 (13.4%)	.97	.441
6	Computer Science journals	137 (91.9%)	12 (8.1%)	.97	.357

Table 4 shows the rating of the items on availability of science journals by students below: Journals on Journals on Microbiology (Mean =1.07) ranked highest in the mean score rating and was followed by Journals on Biochemistry (Mean =1.02), Journals on Chemistry (Mean =.97), Journals on Mathematics/Statistics (Mean =.97), Journals on Biology (Mean =.97) and lastly followed by Journals on Computer Science (Mean =.97).

Research Question 4: To what extent are science journals accessible?

Table 5: Accessibility of Science Journals

S/N	Items	Available	Not Available	Mean	Std. D.
1	Biology journals	132 (88.6%)	17 (11.4%)	.97	.357
2	Microbiology journals.	142 (95.3%)	7 (4.7%)	1.07	.361
3	Chemistry Journals	134 (89.9%)	15 (10.1%)	.97	.441
4	Biochemistry Journals	137 (91.9%)	12 (8.1%)	1.02	.500

5	Mathematics/Statistics Journals	129 (86.6%)	20 (13.4%)	.97	.441
6	Computer Science journals	137 (91.9%)	12 (8.1%)	.97	.357

Table 5 shows the ratings of the items on accessibility of science journals by students below: Journals on Microbiology (Mean =1.07) ranked highest in the mean score rating and was followed by Journals on Biochemistry (Mean =1.02), Journals on Biology (Mean =.97), Journals on Chemistry (Mean =.97), Journals on Mathematics/Statistics (Mean =.97), and lastly Journals on Computer Science (Mean =.97).

Research Question 5: What is the importance of science journals to users?

Table 6: Importance of Science Journals

Items	Yes	Somewhat	Never	Mean	Std.D
It provides me with current and up-to-date information	6 (4.0%)	114 (76.5%)	29 (19.5%)	1.15	.461
It directs and guides me on how to carry out research	108 (72.5%)	36 (24.2%)	5 (3.4%)	1.12	.500
It helps me to carry out quality research	117 (78.5%)	27 (18.1%)	5 (3.4)	1.38	.622
It provides me with the latest research findings in my course of study	91 (61%)	53 (35.6%)	5 (3.4%)	1.25	.505
It helps to develop and improve my intellectual capability	119 (79.8%)	20 (13.4%)	10 (6.7%)	1.23	.627

Table 6 shows the rating of the items on the importance of science journals to students below: It provides me with the latest research findings in my course of study (Mean =1.38), was ranked highest in the mean score rating, and was followed by It help me to carry out quality research (Mean =1.25), It helps to develop and improve my intellectual capability (Mean =1.23), It directs and guild me on how to carry out research (Mean =1.23) and lastly followed by It provides me with current and up-to-date information (Mean =1.15).

Conclusion

Science journals play a pivotal role in providing the research findings of scholars to users in an academic community by promoting and providing the latest and current intellectual and creative works of experts in different fields of knowledge. This means of science communication has provided a broad line in which researcher can advance their area of specialization, and students tap from the flow of their knowledge. However, society has immensely benefited from creating and assimilating new and more enduring knowledge and information. Therefore, the study recommends that university libraries maintain continuous subscriptions and make them available to all fields of knowledge to encourage students' effective use.

Reference

- Agulu, C. C. Aguolu, I. E. (2002) Library and information management in Nigeria. Maidugari: Ed-Linform Services.
- Edelson, A. M. (1998). Editorial: On the Future of Science Journals. American Association for the Advancement of Science Stable. Science, New Series, 280 (5362):359. Available from World Wide Web: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2895136> (Accessed: 02 June 2015)
- Directory of Open Access Repositories (DOAR). 2010. Available from World Wide Web: <http://www.openoar.org> (Accessed 25 April 2015).
- Irenea, K. O., & Sawyerr-George, O. E. (2022). An Assessment of Academic Database Subscription Management in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions: Challenges and Prospects. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-Journal)*, pp. 7419, 1–23. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7419/>
- Koepf, C. (2001). Serial publications. Available from World Wide Web: <http://informatic.buffalo.edu/faculty/ellison/syllbi/519Complete/fmat/s/serials/serials.htm>. (Accessed 21 May, 2015).
- Mohammed, A. (2008). The Development of Academic Journals in Institutions of Higher Learning in Kano State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Available from World Wide Web: <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/210> (Accessed 2 May 2015).
- Moller, A.M. (2006). The case of open access publishing, with special reference to open access journal and their prospects in South Africa. (Unpublished Dissertation, University of Western Cape, South Africa, MA.). Available from World Wide Web: <http://eprints.rclis.org/archive/000518/01/MollerThesis.pdf> (Accessed 2 March 2015).
- Nwalo, K.N. (2003). Fundamentals of Library Practice: A Manual on Library Routine. Ibadan: Stirling-Horden. p. 9.
- Olanlokun, S. O and Salisu, T.M (1988). *Understanding the Library: A Handbook of Library Use*. Lagos: Concept P.47.
- Olurunsola, R. (2001). Book reviews and professional development information: In local and foreign journals, *Middle Belt Journals of Library and Information Science* 1 (1&2): 113- 118
- Oriogu, C.D.; Ogbuiyi, S.U. and Ogbuiyi, D.C. (2014). Availability and accessibility of ICT in the provision of information resources to undergraduate students in Babcock University Library. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol.4, No.14,
- Reitz, J.M. (2004) Dictionary for library and information science. Westport: Greenwood Publishing Group.
- Seiler, L. H. (1990). The Future of the Science Journal. *The Modern Language Journal*, 74 (1): 1–9. Available from World Wide Web: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/327935> (Accessed: 04 June 2015)
- Solomon, D. J. (2013). Digital distribution of academic journals and its impact on science communication: Looking back after 20 years. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*. 39(1 (January 2013), 23 - 28.
- Wang, X. and Su, C. (2006) Open access – philosophy, policy and practice: a comparative study. In *World library and information congress: 72nd IFLA general conference and council, 20-24 August 2006*, (Seoul, Korea, 2006). Available from World Wide Web <http://elpub.scix.net/data/workshop/att/121-elpub2007.content.pdf> (Accessed 19 February, 2015).